

Supplemental information for: Wetting of nanopores probed with pressure

Sanjin Marion,¹ Michal Macha,¹ Sebastian J. Davis,¹ Andrey Chernev,¹ and Aleksandra Radenovic^{1,*}

¹*Laboratory of Nanoscale Biology, Institute of Bioengineering,
School of Engineering, EPFL, 1015 Lausanne, Switzerland*

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S1. DEVICES

Supporting membrane fabrication Wafer processing was subdivided into two major technological steps: a) backside photolithography and etching b) frontside ebeam lithography and etching. The process was performed on the wafers from the same batch (supplier Active Business Company), representing 380 microns thick 100 mm intrinsic Si wafer (100) with 60 nm of SiO₂ and 20 nm low stress SiN on each side. Throughout the first step during the backside photolithography and dry etching apertures for supporting SiN membranes and dicing lines were formed. Next, wet etching through the wafer thickness was done to physically form the supporting SiN membranes and dicing lines. The second technological step was focused on formation of the low-dimensional front side apertures in 20 nm-thick SiN membranes for the suspension of the 2D material¹. For that purpose, e-beam lithography was done using 495A4 PMMA as positive resist at 100 kV. The pattern alignment was done using the wet-etched markers that were formed on the 1st step. The exposed pattern was then transferred to the substrate using a dry etching process in CHF₃/O₂ atmosphere. Ebeam resist was then stripped with a microwave plasma stripper following an acid piranha solution cleaning. To finalize preparation, wafer was rinsed with deionized water.

Samples used in this study Details of the membranes with nanopores which were used in this study are provided in the Table S1. Two membranes were bought from NORCADA (supported membrane size 12 × 12 (±5μ) μm², Silicon Nitride of 20nm±5nm thickness). The in-house chips were produced according to the procedure described above. Different batch runs and membranes had supported membrane sizes ranging from 10 × 10 to 40 × 40 μm². Samples were cleaned before use as described in Table S1. HMDS coated samples were primed on ATMssse hotplate system at 125°C using standard photolithographic process, and were not cleaned prior to use. For samples where MoS₂ was transferred, no cleaning was done before measurement. Transmission electron images of three MoS₂ samples are provided in Fig. S1.

* aleksandra.radenovic@epfl.ch

#	Producer	Pore diameter [nm]	Description
S_h1	Norcada	75 ± 10	HMDS coating (static contact angle 78°), alcohol prewet 20 min
S_h2	In-house	130 ± 10	HMDS coating (static contact angle 84°)
S1	In-house	75 ± 10	5 min O_2 plasma, degass in Schlenk flask
S2	In-house	75 ± 10	5 min O_2 plasma before use, degass in Schlenk flask r
S3	NORCADA	75 ± 10	Reused chip, piranha clean for 2h, degass in Schlenk flask
S4	NORCADA	75 ± 10	5 min O_2 plasma before use, degass in Schlenk flask
S5	NORCADA	75 ± 10	5 min O_2 plasma before use, degass in Schlenk flask
$S_{MoS_2}1$	In-house	No-pore, Fig. S1	MoS ₂ , alcohol prewet for 15 minutes
$S_{MoS_2}2$	In-house	TEM drilled pores, Fig. S1	MoS ₂
$S_{MoS_2}3$	In-house	TEM drilled, Fig. S1	MoS ₂
$S_{MoS_2}4$	In-house	Unknown	MoS ₂
$S_{MoS_2}5$	In-house	Unknown	MoS ₂ , alcohol prewet for 15 minutes

TABLE S1: Table of devices (membranes) used in this study.

(c) Sample $S_{MoS_2}3$

FIG. S1: Transmission electron microscope images of MoS₂ samples before measurements: all samples imaged with FEI TEM Talos at 80 kV in HRTEM mode. Samples $S_{MoS_2}2$ and $S_{MoS_2}3$ drilled by the beam condensation with in-situ control of the pore formation.

S2. AC/DC CURRENT MEASUREMENTS AND ANALYSIS

Phase sensitive measurements (AC) and DC resistance

When performing phase sensitive measurements with the lock-in we use an external driving potential (probe) of the form

$$V(t) = V_0 \sin \omega t \quad (\text{S1})$$

where $\omega = 2\pi f$ with f the frequency of the sine wave. We then measure a response of the form

$$I(t) = I_1 \sin(\omega t + \phi_1) + I_2 \sin(2\omega t + \phi_2) \quad (\text{S2})$$

where the values I_1 and ϕ_1 correspond to the linear (1st harmonic) response and I_2 and ϕ_2 the first correction due to the nonlinear response in the system (2nd harmonic).

The response of the system to our driving voltage $V(t)$ is characterize by the complex valued admittance $Y(\omega, V_0)$ such that

$$I = Y(V)V$$

any non-linearity in the response of the system is in the admittance. We find that at sufficiently low driving voltages and low frequencies, we see no contributions from any non-linearity in capacitance. For small bias voltages ($\ll 1 V_{rms}$) we assume that any non-linearity is found in the conductance $G(V)$:

$$Y(V) = G(V) + j\omega C.$$

At sufficiently low frequencies (below ~ 100 Hz) the capacity C will be dominated by the capacitance of the supporting membrane^{2,3}.

The simplest model for the conductivity would be to take a Taylor expansion for small voltage perturbations which is valid for a purely AC external electric field:

$$G(V) \approx G_0 + G_1 V \quad (\text{S3})$$

with $G(V = 0) = G_0$ and $G_1 = \left(\frac{\partial G(V)}{\partial V}\right)_{V=0}$. Typically $G_1 = 0$ due to time and spatial inversion symmetry, but in the case of nanopores it is known that there can be a break in the symmetry due to ionic current rectification⁴. Previous studies on nanopores⁵ clearly show that the small biasing voltage response is linear and governed by an equation of the form:

$$G_0 = \kappa \sigma$$

with σ the solution conductivity and κ the geometrical factor

$$\kappa^{-1} = \frac{4L}{\pi d^2} + \frac{1}{d}.$$

In contrast to regular impedance spectroscopy where κ corresponds to a cell shape constant, our sample resistance is dominated by the nanopore opening so that κ is the pore shape constant. The dependence of the resistance R of a MoS_2 nanopore on its diameter d is shown on Fig. S1.

Using the nonlinear conductivity model eq. (S3) once can obtain a response to the applied sinisoidal voltage by eq. (S1)

$$I = \frac{1}{2} V_0^2 + (G_0 V_0) \sin(\omega t) + \omega C \cos(\omega t) + \frac{1}{2} G_1 V_0^2 \sin(2\omega t - \frac{\pi}{2})$$

from which we can connect the values measured with the phase sensitive detector eq. (S2) to the phenomenological conductance terms:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &\approx G_0 V_0 \sqrt{1 + \frac{\omega^2 C^2}{G_0^2 V_0^2}} & \phi_1 &= \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\omega C}{G_0 V_0} \right) \\ I_2 &= \frac{1}{2} V_0^2 G_1 & \phi_2 &= -\frac{\pi}{2} \end{aligned}$$

FIG. S2: **Dependence of a MoS₂ nanopore resistance R versus diameter d .** MoS₂ is taken to have a thickness $L = 0.615$ nm. The solution conductivity is taken to be 110 mS/cm.

and calculate the conversion formulas for capacitance C and resistance R_{ac} :

$$R_{ac} = \frac{V_0}{I_1 \cos \phi}$$

$$C = \frac{I_1 \sin \phi}{\omega}$$

An approximation to the current rectification $r(V) = |I(+V)|/|I(-V)|$ at a DC voltage V can be obtained through the higher harmonics of the lock-in signal. Taking into account that the linear conductivity is dominant $G_0 \gg G_1 V$ and that we measure at low (DC-like) frequencies $\omega \ll \frac{G_0 V_0}{C}$:

$$r(V) = \left| \frac{I(+V)}{I(-V)} \right| \approx \frac{G_0 + G_1 V}{G_0 - G_1 V} \approx \frac{I_1 + 2I_2}{I_1 - 2I_2}. \quad (\text{S4})$$

Note that an rectification value obtained from an AC signal, will be according to this definition always $r \geq 1$ so that information about the directionality of the rectification is lost.

As proof that our resistance obtained with AC bias R_{ac} is the same as the DC obtained R we provide control measurements on two different pores ($d \sim 75, 130$ nm) in 20 nm silicon nitride. The IV curves provide the same resistance values as the ones obtained from the AC measurement at frequencies below 10 Hz (Fig. S3).

Pressure and DC/AC data analysis

To obtain a relation between a measured value (I, R_{ac}, C, r) versus pressure P we apply the pressure and once it has settled to within 5% of the target pressure value we wait for at least 1 second for DC current measurements I or 2.5 seconds plus 15 times the settling time base of the lock-in (300 ms - 1 s). Using a CUSUM algorithm implemented in python we identify current segments corresponding to a pressure state. These current segments are then cut so that about the first 70% (to account for settling artifacts) and the last 10% of the segment (to account for synchronisation issues between the lock-in and the pressure system) is excluded. A mean of this signal trace is then used as the representative value at that pressure. This same algorithm is used to extract the noise power spectral densities and the current probability densities (violin plots) from time traces of the current versus applied voltage. In this case, the time trace used for the analysis is at least several seconds long.

FIG. S3: Comparison of DC IV curve and AC measurements on two samples. For the AC response the measured current I_1 and phase ϕ_1 as well as the calculated capacitance C and R_{ac} versus input voltage frequency f are provided. All measurements are done with $V_0 = 0.1 \text{ V}_{rms}$

S3. CAPACITANCE OF SUPPORTED MEMBRANES DURING WETTING

Our aim is to describe how the wetting of the silicon nitride membrane influences its capacitance. The dominant contribution to the chip capacitance obtained through measurements at low AC frequencies comes from a series connection of the double layer capacitance of the silicon nitride membrane and the capacitance of the membrane itself.² Neglecting the contribution of the high resistances, the capacitance C of such a membrane immersed in a salt solution can be approximated as an integral over the whole surface with each small area dA contributing via its local capacitance per unit area \tilde{C}

$$C \approx \iint \tilde{C} dA \quad (\text{S5})$$

where \tilde{C} consists then of a series connection of the silicon nitride membrane \tilde{C}_m and the two electrical double layer contributions \tilde{C}_{dl} :

$$\frac{1}{\tilde{C}} = \frac{1}{\tilde{C}_m} + \frac{2}{\tilde{C}_{dl}}. \quad (\text{S6})$$

The total local capacitance contribution then will be limited by the lowest capacitance in the series, which is in this case the membrane capacitance.²

Let us first discuss the influence of bad wetting on the membrane capacitance \tilde{C}_m . The membrane capacitance can be approximated by a parallel plate capacitor $\tilde{C}_m = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r / d$ with a separation d and a medium of relative permittivity $\epsilon_r \approx 7.5$ for silicon nitride. If a gas bubble covers a surface of area ΔA , then the local capacitance value will be suppressed by the increase in $1/d$ from the added layer of gas, and from the reduction in the local permittivity to a value of $\epsilon_r \approx 1$. We see that already based on this simple argument, the total local capacitance \tilde{C} will be reduced by at least one order of magnitude just based on this scaling argument as it is limited by the reduction of \tilde{C}_m . In that sense, in the first order of approximation a surface air bubble will reduce the contribution to the capacitance proportional to its surface area ΔA . A more detailed analysis would require knowledge of the exact nature and shape of the bubble.

The double layer contribution to the capacitance is proportional to the surface area of the interface between the electrolyte and another medium. Let us take a simple example in which a membrane of surface area A , immersed in a salt solution, has a bubble on one of its surfaces. We will simplify by assuming that the bubble shape is approximated as a spherical cap of radius r , so that the unwetted surface area of the membrane is $a = \pi r^2$. The new surface of the membrane capacitor is now defined by the shape of the bubble on one side, and the membrane surface on the other side. Thus, a spherical bubble will increase the total area of the double layer, but the question is how will the double layer capacitance depend on the effective surface charge and nature of the gas-liquid interface.

To give some insight on the double layer capacitance, we can use a simple model for its differential capacitance. The double layer differential capacitance \tilde{C}_{dl} can be modeled as a series connection of a diffuse layer part \tilde{C}_d and a compact layer part \tilde{C}_c ,⁷ such that:

$$\frac{1}{\tilde{C}_{dl}} = \frac{1}{\tilde{C}_d} + \frac{1}{\tilde{C}_c} \quad (\text{S7})$$

For the diffuse layer capacitance a good model for dilute salt solutions is the Gouy-Chapman theory which gives⁷

$$\tilde{C}_d = \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r}{4\pi \lambda_D} \cosh\left(\frac{e\phi}{2k_B T}\right) \quad (\text{S8})$$

with ϕ the potential drop across the double layer, λ_D the Debye length and $k_B T/e \approx 25.7$ mV. The compact layer capacitance can then be approximated as $\tilde{C}_c = \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_{eff}}{4\pi \delta}$ with δ the distance of closest approach of the ions to the surface and ϵ_{eff} an effective relative permittivity. Importantly, the capacitance depends on the potential drop ϕ , which is directly dependent on the surface charge density at the air-liquid or solid-liquid interface, and will be higher for highly charged surfaces. In our case we know that the surface charge of bubbles in the micron range⁷ is expected to be below the values for the silicon-nitride interface⁶ at the salt and pH conditions we use. We note that this is not necessarily true for nanobubbles⁷, so that for example surface patterned with hydrophobic patches could depending on the conditions lead to an increase in the total capacitance in respect to a membrane not covered with any bubbles. Still, even if the double layer capacitance is increased, it will be limited by the reduction in the membrane capacitance part in the presented model. In our case, we see in Fig. 1c,d that the capacitance increases during bubble absorption, and in no case did we notice that after applying degassed solutions and under compression pressure did the capacitance of the membrane start decreasing after a successful first wetting of the membrane.

S4. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL OF THE NANOPORE WITH OBSTRUCTING OBJECTS

A finite element method was implemented on an axially symmetric system in COMSOL multiphysics (version 5.5). The system was modeled as in^{8,9} by coupled Poisson-Nernst-Planck-Stokes equations. Electrostatic interactions between bound (surface charge on the silicon nitride-water and gas-water interface) and free charges (added salt) were modelled using the Poisson equation for the electrostatic potential $\phi(\mathbf{r})$

$$\nabla^2 \phi(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{\rho(\mathbf{r})}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r} \quad (\text{S9})$$

with $\rho(\mathbf{r}) = eN_a \sum_i z_i c_i(\mathbf{r})$ the density of free charge carriers with z_i the valency and c_i the density in mol/m^3 of the ion i , and ϵ_r the relative permittivity of the material (80 for water, 7.7 for silicon nitride, 1 for air). Here the free charge densities c_i were subject to the Nernst-Planck equations for the ion flux \mathbf{J}_i of species i with convection due to fluid flow with a velocity $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r})$:

$$\mathbf{J}_i = -D_i \nabla c_i - \frac{D_i}{k_B T} z_i e c_i \nabla \phi(\mathbf{r}) + c_i \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (\text{S10})$$

where D_i are the diffusion constants for the ions ($D_1 = D_2 = 2 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$).

Fluid flow was obtained using the Stokes equation with an electric body force $\rho(\mathbf{r})\nabla\phi(\mathbf{r})$ and pressure gradient ∇p :

$$\eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} = \rho(\mathbf{r})\nabla\phi(\mathbf{r}) + \nabla p \quad (\text{S11})$$

with η the dynamic viscosity of water using the built in COMSOL parameters.

The FEM mesh was constructed in COMSOL similar to previous works⁸⁻¹⁰ using boundary layer refinement with minimal size at boundaries of 0.1 nm and growth ratio of 1.2. Near all corners and at the nanopore opening the mesh was additionally refined until convergence was obtained. First a 1D problem on the boundary of the simulation domain was solved without fluid flow and then used as the boundary condition for the full problem⁸, with pressure applied on all the external boundaries on both sides of the chamber.

We studied four possible cases of nanopores representing: a) an open pore (Fig. S4), a pore with an obstruction (bubble) sitting at the pore edge on one side of the chamber (Fig. S5), a pore with a circular obstruction (clog) (Fig. S6) and a pore with a spherical unwetted part constricting the pore (Fig. S5). In all cases the supported silicon nitride membrane was taken to be 20 nm thick with a nanopore diameter of $d = 40 \text{ nm}$. The air bubble was taken to have a radius of $r_b = 80 \text{ nm}$ and the electrolyte concentration to be $c = 1 \text{ M}$. The surface charge at the solid-liquid interface (silicon nitride to water) was taken to be $\sigma_{ls} = 50 \text{ mC}/\text{m}^2$ and the charge at the gas-liquid interface (air bubble to water) was taken to be $\sigma_{gs} = 20 \text{ mC}/\text{m}^2$, in accordance with zeta potential measurements on silicon nitride pores⁶ and microbubbles⁷. We note that a larger surface charge in the case of the air-gas liquid interface would only enhance ionic current rectification. Details about each simulation are provided in the figure captions.

In order to probe for how the four static cases of obstructions at the nanopore influence the conductance, we extract the total current going through the system at different bias voltages (from -300 mV to 300 mV) and under different pressure gradients ($P = 0, \pm 5 \text{ bar}$). Fig. S8a shows the current versus voltage curves (IV) for an open pore compared to the bubble case. An open pore is seen to have zero ionic current rectification ($r = 1$) under no pressure, and a small level of ionic current rectification under a pressure gradient which comes from the convective contribution to the ion transport ($r < 1.005$). In comparison, in the same geometry but with a bubble present on the side we see that there is a measurable ionic current rectification ($r = 1.014$) which is reduced under pressure gradient. This effect has already been well documented in the literature^{11,12}, and is explained as coming from the fluid flow destroying the concentration polarization effect inside the pore arising from the asymmetry of the nanopore and the presence of surface charges. In the case of a clog particle (Fig. S8a) we see that the pressure gradient is not sufficient to reduce the ionic current rectification completely from its zero pressure value ($r = 0.97$) but it modulates the value. This is also in accordance with known results that if the rectifying nanopore is too small, the fluid flow rate is not sufficient to nullify the ionic current rectifying effect of the concentration polarization.¹¹ In this case, conduction is proceeding through a thin ring formed at the point of closest separation which due to access effects limits the total fluid flow. Lastly, we find that in the case of a symmetrical unwetted pore (Fig. S8c) we have no ionic current rectification ($r = 1$). In all three cases, the resistance of the nanopore is increased by the presence of the obstruction, but the conductance stays linear in respect to the applied voltage.

We conclude that neither of the static models presented here can account for the large change in ionic rectification and resistance, as seen in the main text, but that a dynamic model is required. We suggest that the most likely scenario is that due to improper wetting, a nanobubble is moved around the entrance and deformed by the pressure driven fluid flow.

FIG. S4: **FEM model of a unobstructed nanopore (open pore case)**. Surface profiles are provided for the case of an applied potential difference of 300 mV. Black circles mark the areas where the mesh was additionally refined. The system has axial symmetry around the center of the nanopore. One can see on panel (a) that the majority of the potential drop is concentrated at the nanopore entrance area and inside the nanopore. Panel (b) shows the magnitude of the electroosmotic flow velocity in this case.

FIG. S5: **FEM model of a air bubble on one side of the nanopore (bubble cas)**. The same as in Fig. S4, except an gaseous air bubble was placed next to the nanopore opening on one side. Panel (b) shows how the electroosmotic flow distribution around the nanopore opening is no longer symmetrical. Note that due to the axial symmetry the surface nanobubble is actually "doughnut"-shaped.

FIG. S6: **FEM model of an object (air) obstructing the entrance of the nanopore (clog case).** The same as in Fig. S4, except an gaseous obstruction was placed at the pore opening, almost completely obstructing it. The distance of closes separation between the spherical obstruction and the silicon nitride membrane was chosen to be ≈ 4 nm so as to enable easy convergence at the double layer region on the boundaries.

FIG. S7: **FEM model of a nanopore entrance obstructed by a symmetrical air bubble (unwetted case).** The same as in Fig. S4, except an gaseous obstruction was placed at the pore opening so that it is constricting the pore size. The resulting radius of the opening was chosen to be 10 nm in radius, with the center of the gas obstruction shifted by 40 nm from the center of the simulation box.

(a) Comparison between open pore (Fig. S4) and the bubble case (Fig. S5).

(b) Comparison between open pore (Fig. S4) and clog case (Fig. S6).

(c) Comparison between open pore (Fig. S4) and the unwell case (Fig. S7).

FIG. S8: Current versus voltage curves extracted from the FEM models representing the open nanopore case (Fig. S4), bubble case (Fig. S5), clogged case (Fig. S6), and unwell case (Fig. S7). Figure legend note the level of applied pressure gradient (P), and the resulting ionic current rectification (r) and pore resistance (R).

S5. WETTING HYDROPHOBIC PORES SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

FIG. S9: **Sample S_h1: Pressure wetting after V sweeps.** Figure shows wetting of the sample with compression pressure P_c performed after several hours of IV curves in the range of ± 10 V. This measurement was performed under $0.1 V_{RMS}$ of AC bias. Note that a compression pressure of $P_c \approx 1$ bar is sufficient to achieve wetting. This sample has a worse hydrophobic coating than the sample presented in Fig. 2 of the main text (static contact angle ≈ 78). We attribute a worse hydrophobic coating or damage due to prolonged exposure to high voltages as the cause for easier wetting in spite of a smaller expected pore size and possible variations in the production method. The lack of settling of the capacitance C a stable value is attributed to surface bubbles due to the use of alcohol prewetting. The time trace for this measurement is provided in Fig. S37.

FIG. S10: Sample S_h2 : Time trace for Fig. 2c,d in the main text.

FIG. S11: Sample S_h2 : DC current versus pressure for sample in Fig. 2c,d. Dependence of the DC resistance versus applied pressure measured at +3 V bias voltage. Measurement was performed approximately 50 minutes before Fig. 2c,d. Time trace provided in Fig. S38.

S6. WETTING ARTIFACTS IN HYDROPHILIC PORES SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Sample S1: We provide the full time trace of the measured AC data for Fig. 3c (Fig. S12) , as well as a DC pressure sweep performed after that measurement (Fig. S13). Sample was filled with incompletely degassed solution by pipetting from Schlenk flasks into syringes.

FIG. S12: **Sample S1: Time trace for Fig. 3c** Raw time trace of the applied pressure and the measured R_{ac} , C and r .

Sample S2: Sample was filled with incompletely degassed solution by pipetting from Schlenk flasks into syringes. After filling the sample presented similar behaviour as in Fig. 3 of the main text. Fig. S14 shows how the system IV curve changed from a linear ($\Delta P = 0$) to a nonlinear IV curve under the application of pressure ($\Delta P \pm 3$ bar), ending in a partially closed state at the end ($\Delta P = 0$). The power spectral density (PSD) indicates an increase in noise during this process, with the lowest noise in the open starting state, followed by the ending partially clogged state, with the both states under pressure expressing a higher level of Flicker noise. A pressure sweep (Fig. S15) showed that the capacitance was stable, but that the same direction which caused the unwetting of the pore is also increasing both the resistance R_{AC} and ionic current rectification r as measured with an AC stimuli, with the state at $P = 0$ indicating good wetting.

Sample S3: Sample was filled with incompletely degassed solution by pipetting from Schlenk flasks into syringes. After filling the sample picked up a bubble/obstruction under pressure (Fig. S16) which resembles the same profile as in Fig. 3c but with a higher resistance value. IV curves performed after this indicate that the nanopore is not completely wetted and that the noise level is highest when a pressure gradient of the opposite direction than the one which caused a bubble pick-up is applied (Fig. S17). After flushing with freshly degassed solution and applying compression pressure for several minutes the nanopore IV curve linearized (S16). As the chip was reused, we can not confirm that the chip hasn't at least partially clogged.

Sample S4: Sample was filled with incompletely degassed solution by pipetting from Schlenk flasks into syringes. After compression filling, the system exhibited IV curves which were changing in time (Fig. S19). We then performed

FIG. S13: **Sample S1.** Sweep of DC current I at 0.1 V versus gradient pressure performed after Fig. 3c,d (Fig. S12) in the main text. An IV curve measured before this indicated the resistance was close to the open value and that the bubble has left the pore during this measurement. This pressure sweep indicates that it might have been flushed through the pore. Raw time trace is provided in Fig. S39.

FIG. S14: **Sample S2: Example of pressure switching of a bubble in the nanopore.** An IV curve is provided for four subsequent measurements done under an applied pressure of $\Delta P = 0, 3, -3, 0$ bar. Right panel is a current power spectral density obtained from the first point in the IV curve at 0.2 V. Note that the open pore is moved into a closed state with positive pressure. A negative pressure partially recovers the open state with a lower noise than with positive pressure, but higher than in the original open state, and with strong ionic current rectification. After this the pore is still in a closed state but with a lower noise level than when either the positive or negative pressure was applied.

compression pressure which indicated no change in the indicators (Fig. S20). If a pressure gradient was applied, the sample resistance decreased under negative pressure with a reduction in ionic current rectification r .

Sample S5: Sample was filled with incompletely degassed solution by pipetting from a Schlenk flask into a syringe. Sample was filled using compression pressure, after which an application of a pressure gradient reduced the resistance (Fig. S21). This was followed with an increase in noise, as expected for bad wetting. A pressure sweep (Fig. S22) indicates there was a temporary blockage which was flushed.

FIG. S15: Sample S2: Pressure switching of the bubble measured 2h after Fig. S14.

FIG. S16: Sample S3: Example of a pressure switching of a bubble inside the nanopore. Note that this measurement was done at a frequency $f = 11$ Hz, and due to operator error the Faraday cage was improperly closed so that the rectification r data is present only from the moment it was closed due to too high noise. The sample returns to a higher value of 10 MΩ as it was reused and cleaned in Piranha for 2h after being immersed in salt previously. This might have increased the hydrophobicity of the pore, but also could have cause clogging artifacts to be present.

FIG. S17: **Sample S3: IV curve showing pressure gating of a pore.** IV curves measured under gradient pressures of $\Delta P = -5, 0, 5, 0$ bar in chronological order performed after the measurement presented in Fig. S16. The current power spectral density is shown in the right panel. Note that in this case the lowest level of noise is obtained under a pressure of $\Delta P = -5$ bar.

FIG. S18: **Sample S3: IV curve showing the state of the sample after Fig. S17 and after flushing with more degassed solution and applying compression pressure.** The solution used was obtained by degassing under vacuum in a Schlenk flask immersed in a cold bath in a sonicator for 30 minutes. It was then gently transferred to a syringe and used to flush the solution. The dashed line presents a linear fit corresponding to sample resistance $R = 5 \text{ M}\Omega$. The right panel is the current power spectral density at $+0.2 \text{ V}$.

FIG. S19: **Sample S4: Time evolution of an IV curve.** Note that the starting lower resistance curves are slowly fluctuating into the high resistance curves. Current power spectral density is provided on the right panel as extracted from them at +0.2 V.

FIG. S20: **Sample S4: Pressure dependence of R_{ac} , C and r obtained after Fig. S19.** The measurement in the blue-red color scheme was done with compression pressure P_c , while the other measurement was done with pressure gradients, in that chronological order. Compression pressure did not modify the state of the pore, while the application of a pressure gradient changed the pore first into a more resistive, and then into a more open state. Note that the wait time and time constant for the lock-in was too low so that the measurement had a higher level of imprecision. Time trace of the measurement is provided in Fig. S41.

FIG. S21: **Sample S5: Example of bubble pick-up due to pressure.** The first IV curve is recorded immediately after filling (linear fit to a resistance of $R = 1.12$ M Ω), and the second one is recorder under a pressure of $\Delta P = 7$ bar (linear fit to a resistance of $R = 4.0$ M Ω). A pressure sweep depicted on Fig. S22, and a compression sweep with no visible effect was done between these two measurements. In the obstructed case the noise power spectral density provided in the right panel increases significantly.

FIG. S22: **Sample S5: Pressure sweep done between the two measured IV curves on Fig. S21.** This measurement was done at $f = 11$ Hz. No time trace is available due to operator error.

S7. WETTING ARTIFACTS WITH 2D MATERIALS SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Sample $S_{MoS_2}1$: The sample was TEM imaged and no pores were found. After that the sample was put in a 1:1 ethanol and de-ionized water for 20 minutes, before being placed into the chamber and filled with 1M KCl solution buffered at pH 8 (as described in the Methods section of the main text). We found that the system filled under compression pressure, indicating an nonlinear IV curve which was consistent with the application of gradient pressures (Fig. S23) with a high level of noise present and instabilities in the current levels. Even though we applied voltages larger than the limit for electrochemical enlargement of the pores (> 0.75 V)¹³, there was no change in the behavior in time suggesting that the exposed pore area is not due to MoS₂. The nonlinearity of the curve matches the models for gas bubble temporary electrowetting by Smirnov et al.¹⁴. We interpret this as a wetting issue (air bubble) over the membrane due to the use of alcohol prewetting, which the original MoS₂ membrane possibly damaged.

FIG. S23: **Sample $S_{MoS_2}1$: Nonlinear IV curves versus applied pressure.** This sample was confirmed to have no pores by TEM imaging before this measurement. Note that this sample was prewetted with alcohol and then flushed with degassed solution. IV curves and noise power spectral densities (right panel, at +0.2 V) are given under three different pressure gradients $\Delta P = 0, 3.5, -3.5$ bar showing no significant pressure dependence. Further application of compression pressure and flushing degassed solution did not change the state of the system until the membrane broke. The IV curve in the range of ± 0.5 V would indicate a nanopore in the ~ 1 nm range. We interpret this as being a wetting issue due to the alcohol prewetting.

Sample $S_{MoS_2}2$: The sample was imaged in TEM and drilled to have a pore of about $d \approx 3 - 4$ nm with at least one smaller satellite pore. The pore was filled with degassed 1M KCl buffered at pH8 as described in the main text. After the application of 7 bar compression pressure, its current versus voltage characteristic was measured with the voltage always lower than the voltages known to cause electrochemical enlarging of the pores (< 0.75 V)¹³. Time evolution of the IV curves in the system indicated that the current levels were fluctuating between several states in time (Fig. S24) with the most conductive state corresponding to roughly the expected pore resistance based on the TEM imaging. All these curves had the same level of Flicker noise. The sample was then flushed with freshly degassed solution and compression pressure was applied for several minutes. All the IV curves linearized and each further application of compression pressure was changing the pore resistance (Fig. S25), with the high resistance state having the largest Flicker noise level. We believe this was a nanobubble pinned near the pore entrance (wetting issue) which was being slowly dissolved by applying compression pressure and a degassed solution. The original pore in MoS₂ possibly enlarged during handling (as it had at least one smaller satellite pore) or the membrane broke.

Sample $S_{MoS_2}3$: The sample was imaged in TEM and drilled to have several pore of several nanometers in diameter. The pore was filled with degassed 1M KCl buffered at pH8 as described in the main text. After the application of 7 bar compression pressure for several minutes it demonstrated a fluctuating nonlinear IV curve (Fig. S26) which relaxed in time to a higher resistance and noise level matching the trends shown in the first IV curve (Fig. S27). After about 12h of wait, the system exhibited a stable and more conductive nonlinear IV curve (Fig. 4a in the main text), which was then linearized with compression pressure and flushing with fresh degassed solutions (Fig. 4b). The sample showed a stable level of resistance with minor fluctuations at high negative pressures (Fig. S28). After that a solvent exchange with ethanol was performed which increased the resistance. Application of a pressure gradient in this state

FIG. S24: **Sample $S_{\text{MoS}_2 2}$: fluctuating IV curves immediately after filling.** Three IV curves recorded about 10 minutes apart show fluctuations between a highly rectifying and almost linear IV curve. Power spectral densities of the ionic currents shown on the right panel indicate no significant difference in the flicker noise of the sample during this evolution. The most linear curve would correspond to a resistance of $R \approx 25 \text{ M}\Omega$, or to a MoS_2 pore of size $d \approx 4 \text{ nm}$. Based on the drilled TEM image we would expect the pore to have a size of $d \approx 3 - 4 \text{ nm}$.

FIG. S25: **Sample $S_{\text{MoS}_2 2}$: After flushing the sample from Fig. S24 with degassed solution and compressing at 7 bar.** We first obtain a linear IV curve with a resistance of $R = 5.9 \text{ M}\Omega$ (MoS_2 pore of diameter $d = 15 \text{ nm}$). After applying more compression pressure we see that the resistance increases to $R = 15.1 \text{ M}\Omega$ (MoS_2 pore of diameter $d = 7 \text{ nm}$). After further applying 7 bar compression, the resistance went to $R = 1.5 \text{ M}\Omega$ corresponding to the resistance of the supporting nanopore in silicon nitride.

indicated that there were wetting issues (Fig. S29).

Sample $S_{\text{MoS}_2 4}$: The membrane was filled with degassed 1M KCl buffered at pH8 as described in the main text. After the application of 7 bar compression pressure for several minutes. First measurements indicated a high resistive IV curve (Fig. S30) which was fluctuating between levels indicating current levels comparable to just the supporting membrane with no MoS_2 present (Fig. S31). Under low voltages the pore indicated less fluctuations in the current level (Fig. S32). Based on this we conclude there are wetting issues due to the presence of gas bubbles and possible other contaminants. Application of pressure gradients and compression pressure (Fig. S33) indicate that under compression the resistance of the pore is stable and high, but that gradient pressure moves the pore between low and high resistances, with the low resistance state indicating a low level of ionic current rectification indicating

FIG. S26: **Sample $S_{\text{MoS}_2}3$: Immediately after filling and a day before the measurements in Fig. 4a,b of the main text.** The bars denote extrema of the current probability density distributions, while the shapes denote the probability density for finding the current at that value (violin plot). The amplifier range was limited to measuring ± 10 nA.

FIG. S27: **Sample $S_{\text{MoS}_2}3$: Time evolution of the IV curve from Fig. S26.** During this time the IV curve was let to settle with no disturbances. Further applications of pressure in the range of ± 3 bar did not change the IV curve shape. If one were to extrapolate the resistance of these pores in the ± 0.2 V range one would obtain resistances (and effective MoS_2 diameters) of $140 \text{ M}\Omega$ (1.1 nm) and for the last two curves $500 \text{ M}\Omega$ (0.5 nm). Yet, from TEM images we expect a nanopore in the several nm size range. The noise power spectral density (right panel) increased considerably during the time that the apparent resistance also increased and fluctuations of the current reduced. Note that the amplifier noise in this current range is about $20 \text{ fA}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$.

better wetting.

Sample $S_{\text{MoS}_2}5$: The sample was put in a 1:1 ethanol and de-ionized water for 20 minutes, before being placed into the chamber and filled with 1M KCl solution buffered at pH 8 (as described in the Methods section of the main text). After filling, the system was found to be switchable between two states (Fig. 4c,d,e and Fig. S34 as described in the main text). Two subsequent DC measurement of the current versus voltage under a pressure sweep are provided (Fig. S35,S36), matching the AC measurements.

FIG. S28: Sample $S_{MoS_2}3$: Pressure sweep of DC current done before the solvent exchange but after the flushing with the degassed solution in Fig. 4b of the main text. A time trace of this curve is provided in Fig. S42.

FIG. S29: Sample $S_{MoS_2}3$: AC pressure sweep done after the solvent exchange curve on Fig. 4b in the main text. Note that the second measurement is done under compression pressure. Time traces for this figure are given in Fig. S43

FIG. S30: **Sample $S_{MoS_2}4$: Immediately after filling of the chamber.** The bars indicate extrema and the mean value while the shape of the curve represents the current probability density (violin plot). The system stayed in this state for an hour or more without any noticeable change in the noise spectrum.

FIG. S31: **Sample $S_{MoS_2}4$: Testing the sample with voltages up to 0.7 V a day after Fig. S30.** The bars indicate extrema and the mean value while the shape of the curve represents the current probability density (violin plot). The voltage was not varied in a regular way as in all other IV curves. Note that the applied voltages in this stage were below the reported voltages expected to cause an electrochemical reaction $(0.75 \text{ V})^{13}$. Note the high level of current fluctuations especially above 0.3 V. We attribute this to bubble or wetting/dewetting fluctuations.

FIG. S32: **Sample $S_{MoS_2}4$: fluctuating IV curves after applying higher voltages in Fig. S31.** The right panel shows how a high level of fluctuations for the 2nd measurement at +0.2 V is followed by also a high level of flicker noise as expected due to the presence of nanobubbles.

FIG. S33: **Sample $S_{MoS_2}4$: AC Pressure sweeps done after Fig. S32.** The first measurement is done using compression pressure and shows no change of the IV curves between two states, while in the gradient pressure the resistance changes between two states with a different state stable under no applied pressure. The lowest resistance state at $P < 0$ has no ionic current rectification.

FIG. S34: **Sample $S_{\text{MoS}_2}5$** : IV curves from which the current power spectral density in Fig. 4e of the main text was obtained..

FIG. S35: **Sample $S_{\text{MoS}_2}5$** : DC pressure sweep done after the Fig. 4c,d in the main text. This curve confirms that the switching behavior seen in the AC measurement is not an artifact of using AC current for the measurement. The curve is obtained at a 0.1 V DC bias. The time trace for this curve is provided in Fig. S46.

FIG. S36: **Sample $S_{MoS_2}5$: DC pressure sweep done after the Fig. 4c,d in the main text.** This curve confirms that the switching behavior seen in the AC measurement is not an artifact of using AC current for the measurement. The curve is obtained at a 0.1 V DC bias. The time trace for this curve is provided in Fig. S46.

S8. ADDITIONAL DATA

FIG. S37: Sample S_{h1} : Pressure wetting after voltage sweeps. Time trace for Fig. S9.

FIG. S38: **Sample S_{h2}**: DC current versus pressure for sample in Fig. 2c,d. Time trace for Fig. S11. Note that the curve is obtained under a DC bias of 3V.

FIG. S39: **Sample S1**. Raw time trace for Fig. S13.

FIG. S40: **Sample S2: Pressure switching of the bubble measured 2h after Fig. S14.** Time trace of Fig. S15.

FIG. S41: Sample S4: Time trace of S20.

FIG. S42: Sample $S_{MoS_2}3$: Time trace of Fig. S28

FIG. S43: Sample $S_{MoS_2}3$: Time trace of Fig. S29.

FIG. S44: Sample $S_{MoS_2} 4$: Time trace for Fig. S33.

FIG. S45: Sample S_{MoS_2} 5: Time trace of the AC pressure sweep shown in the Fig. 4c,d of the main text.

FIG. S46: Sample $S_{MoS_2}5$.

FIG. S47: Sample $S_{MoS_2}5$: Time trace for Fig. S36.

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